

THE CONCEPT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, the purposes and objectives of inclusive education and the basics of inclusive education are described. Inclusive education is a process that aims to integrate disabled children into the educational process and adapt general education schools to disabled children, taking into account social justice and equality. Inclusive education includes children with special needs and disabilities not only in special schools but also admits that they can be educated in general schools. For this, both the school and the teachers-educators should be ready for the inclusive education system, and the school level, physical conditions, and the factors that make it possible to study should fully meet these educational requirements.

Keywords: inclusive education, integration, social adaption, conditions, children with disabilities, schools, special education, general education.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada inklyuziv ta'limning maqsad va vazifalari hamda inklyuziv ta'lim asoslari bayon etilgan. Inklyuziv ta'lim - bu ijtimoiy adolat va tenglikni hisobga olgan holda nogiron bolalarni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiyalash va umumiy ta'lim maktablarini nogiron bolalarga moslashtirishga qaratilgan jarayondir. Inklyuziv ta'lim alohida ehtiyojli va nogiron bolalarni nafaqat maxsus maktablarda, balki ular umumiy maktablarda ham ta'lim olishlarini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Buning uchun maktab ham, o'qituvchi-pedagog ham inklyuziv ta'lim tizimiga tayyor bo'lishi, maktab darajasi, jismoniy sharoiti, o'qish imkonini beruvchi omillar ana shu ta'lim talablariga to'liq javob berishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: *inklyuziv ta'lim, integratsiya, ijtimoiy moslashuv, sharoitlar, imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar, maktablar, maxsus ta'lim, umumiy ta'lim.*

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны цели и задачи инклюзивного образования, а также основы инклюзивного образования. Инклюзивное образование – это процесс, целью которого является интеграция детей-инвалидов в образовательный процесс и адаптация общеобразовательных школ к детям-инвалидам с учетом социальной справедливости и равенства. Инклюзивное образование включает детей с особыми потребностями и ограниченными

возможностями не только в специальные школы, но и допускает возможность их обучения в общеобразовательных школах. Для этого и школа, и педагоги-воспитатели должны быть готовы к системе инклюзивного образования, а уровень школы, физические условия и факторы, позволяющие учиться, должны полностью соответствовать этим образовательным требованиям.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное образование, интеграция, социальная адаптация, условия, дети с ограниченными возможностями, школы, специальное образование, общее образование.

Inclusive education means that all children receive education in the same school and the same classroom - under the same conditions. That is, a child with disabilities should be able to study with the same attention as healthy children. In Uzbekistan, regardless of family circumstances, all children attend state comprehensive schools. It is guaranteed by the state. Sometimes, if we see children with disabilities among our peers, schoolmates, or in the neighborhood, without understanding, we try to isolate them and not communicate with them. This is wrong, in fact, if we become friends with them and live as a community, we can contribute to their happy lives. Every child in society has the right to be happy! [1]

The goal of inclusive education is to create a barrier-free, adapted educational environment for students with special educational needs, by using special tools and methods at school, involving special pedagogues, their effective adaptation to society, and full-fledged development. is to provide high-quality general secondary education that serves the harmonization. Schools provide comprehensive support to children with special educational needs and their parents in receiving corrective pedagogical support and career guidance.

The tasks of inclusive education are as follows:

- creating a single adapted social environment that excludes any discrimination and ensures equal treatment of all children for students with different development opportunities;
- forming a tolerant attitude towards the problems of students with special educational needs in the public and all participants in the educational process;
- development of the mental and social potential of children with special educational needs along with healthy children in the educational process;
- creating an opportunity for all students to master general secondary education programs by state educational standards;
- creating conditions for the all-round development of students, activation of an emotional and volitional sphere, cognitive activity, formation of social skills and potential;

- Provide counseling support to families raising children with special educational needs and raise awareness of parents in the field of education and upbringing of their children, the use of pedagogical technologies, educational methods, and tools, and psychological and pedagogical support. [2]

The education of children with special needs in the special education system makes it difficult for them to adapt to society after finishing school. In addition, children with special disabilities have to live far from their families, since they are educated at the special boarding schools. It can often lead to them feeling isolated and alone which makes it even more difficult for them to adapt to society.

In addition, there are many people with special needs children who are left out of education. Currently, in our Republic, an inclusive education policy is being implemented in order to make children with special needs receive education in special or general education systems according to their development level, characteristics of disabilities, and abilities. Placing a disabled child in normal conditions is the first step towards integration. Inclusive education is based on the social model and considers the problem not in the child, but in the program and methodology. This requires making some changes to the education system. In this case, educational plans are prepared taking into account the needs of each child, and aspects of the methodology related to psychological problems are put on the right track. Inclusive education concludes that all children, including disabled children, can study in the school they want. Therefore, this society must sacrifice itself for his education. In inclusive education, the physical conditions at school also play an important role. To put it simply, students enter the doors of all schools through the stairs. However disabled children in special wheelchairs cannot climb these stairs, even children on crutches may have difficulty. Therefore, it is necessary to create comfortable conditions for healthy children and disabled children to pass through the stairs and doors. Inclusive education allows children with special needs to always be in their family neighborhood and the circle of relatives. The placement of children in boarding schools far away from their family and home prevents their right to participate in the life of their home, family, and community. A child who is far from his home, family, and parental love grows up hard. Because the family is the main center of education. Inclusive education can catalyze improving the quality of education. [3]

Admission of children with special needs to general education institutions encourages students to develop new teaching methods that are more child-centered and more inclusive. And the benefit of this affects every child. Inclusive education helps prevent discrimination. In society, there is a very high misconception and attitude towards disabled people. The reason for this may be the lack of information about them and their

closed education in special institutions from a young age. Losing or reducing such an attitude is a very difficult task. But it is known from experience that compared to adults, children understand differences and similarities faster. If children with special needs were educated together with children with normal development, it would ensure that all children with disabilities would realize that they are children like themselves and would not be discriminated against. [4] One of the most urgent problems today is the issue of important tasks and the situation in the system related to children in need of social protection. After the independence of Uzbekistan, as in all areas, deep reforms and changes are taking place in the system of social protection of children. The interpretation of new ideas on inclusive education requires national, organizational, and methodological reforms. Children with special educational needs are children whose needs are not being met by the current school system. For this reason, schools must respond to the diverse and common goals, aspirations, and interests of all children and ensure their education. [5]

In the past twenty years of education of children with special needs in the system of general education institutions, considerable work has been done. But the main thing is to introduce an inclusive education system on the scale of cities, and still special support in rural areas needy children are left out of education, or parents in villages are disabled to ensure that their children attend special institutions in cities are facing difficulties. Therefore, for children in need of special assistance children with special needs in all regions inclusive education, it should be ensured that it is covered. Principle of Link Availability.

Disrupting the normal development of a child with special needs can lead to more serious conditions than disability. Complex in inclusive education principle of approach. Children in need of special assistance are considered disabled It is necessary to approach these children in all aspects, rather than to approach them from the point of view. This is when planning education for children with special needs making a plan taking into account the needs that may arise during his life. At the core of this principle, children need help early in their early years' approach also lies. Education of children with special needs should not end with primary and secondary special education. Children with special needs Vocational education and higher education also require implementation. Inclusive education`s one of the tasks of the system is to comprehensively provide children with special needs development to ensure all their rights. [5]

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